

How Do Social Workers Support Mothers Whose Babies Are Being Removed at Birth?

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13866619 | ISSN: 2977-1676

The Journal of
Crime & Justice
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www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13866619>

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Abstract

This literature review examines the support social workers provide to mothers whose babies are removed at birth. With a focus on those mothers who have experienced the care system themselves, this research aims to identify existing support structures and evaluate their effectiveness. The review highlights the significant increase in newborn removals and explores the sociological concept of zemiology to understand the broader social harms involved. It examines the prenatal, antenatal, postnatal, and post-court proceedings stages to identify gaps in support and suggest improvements. The findings indicate a need for more consistent and ethical support systems, addressing the trauma and adverse childhood experiences that many of these mothers have faced. The review concludes with recommendations for a trauma-informed approach and the necessity of mandatory support for these vulnerable mothers to break the cycle of repeated removals.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This Literature review looks at how social workers support mothers who have had their babies or children removed. Pause, (2023) state that almost 47% of new-borns in the care system, were born to mothers who have themselves previously been through the care system, strikingly this is almost half of the total number, and inspired me to focus on those mothers who have been known to the care system or known to social services within their childhood. The aim of this research is to identify what support, is being offered to mothers. According to the Guardian, over a five-year period from 2008-2013, the number of new-borns removed from their mothers increased by two and a half times (Tickle, 2016). This would suggest that the support currently offered is having little effect in reducing the number of children being removed from their mother's care. Additionally, this review will consider a zemiological lens within the discussion, zemiology is understood to be the study of social harm. Canning and Tombes (2021, as cited in Wroe 2022) suggest zemiology, as a study of the policies, structures and practices, that have a negative harmful impact on people. This sociological approach will consider the mothers, as a victim of crime with the perpetrators being the decision makers of the policies, structures, and practices.

1.2 Background

According to the charity 'Become' there were 107,317 children in social care across the UK, in March 2023, with 83,840 of those children in care in England. When comparing this to the 2001 census, that is an increase from 44 children in every 10,000 to 71 in every 10,000. Statistics reported by Gov.uk 2023 state there was an increase of 2% of children looked after, in 2022 there were 82,170 with this figure rising to 83,840 in March 2023 (Gov.uk, 2023). These figures highlighting over a 10-year period the numbers of children who are looked after is still on the rise despite current interventions.

Children come into care for many reasons; the most known reasons why social worker intervention is required are due to, neglect, physical and emotional abuse and domestic violence abuse (Become.org). Section 31 of the Children Act 1989 states that the local authority may make an application to court for a care or supervision order, and that the court will make this order once satisfied that the child concerned is suffering or likely to suffer significant harm, should the order not be issued. (CA1989)

According to the institute for government (Fright & Davies, 2023), performance tracker the number of referrals of children in care has risen to pre-pandemic levels with a rise between 2009/10 and 2020/21 of 43%. The data suggests an overall increase in demand on children's services. This squeeze on children's services has caused a 73% decline in the spending on preventative measures such as Sure Start Children Centres (Fright & Davies, 2023). Sure start was introduced by a Labour policy in 1998, and saw outreach services such as play and healthcare being delivered to under 5-year-olds and families in the most deprived areas. Sure start's aim was to improve children's outcomes, yet since the removal of the ringfenced funding in 2011, most local authorities have chosen to make the budgeting decision to close these centres (Cattan et al., 2019). Local authorities across the UK, all receive funding from a range of sources; some of the money is accountable, meaning that local authorities have a say on how funding is used locally. Some local authorities, because of the rising number of children at risk, are under immense financial strain and are cutting back on vital services needed within social care, meaning little is invested where it is needed most to address the root causes of this issue. (National Audit Office, 2017).

In 2021/22, £11.1 billion was spent by local authorities in children's social care. This sustained increase in spending compared to previous years, in children's social care continues to negatively affect the budget for other children's services (Fright & Davies, 2023). For this research I would like to consider the repeated removal of children from the same mother.

Research between 2007 and 2014 states over 11,000 mothers had more than one baby removed, and over 40% of these mothers had previously experienced some form of social care, either being placed in foster care or a children's home, as a child themselves (Nuffield foundation, 2017).

The Pause project believes that no family should experience the removal of a child more than once. Mothers who have experienced the removal of their child from their care experience a range of inequalities such as social exclusion, vulnerability to poverty and homelessness and a range of health issues, such as emotional devastation, trauma, and mental health distress (Pause, 2023).

I intend to research what preventative measures are in place to try and help the mothers who have already had a baby removed. I will evaluate current provision and also gain an understanding of the potential outcome should preventative measure be introduced, such as time and money spent on helping a mother to meet her needs.

I want to explore the effects on a mother when having a baby removed, a mother who has potentially bonded with her unborn child. At present, a children's social worker focuses on the mother's lifestyle and health in order to protect her unborn baby, then the social worker and the social service system transfer that focus on to the new-born baby (Broadhurst & Mason, 2017). Additionally, I would like to research if enough help and support is indeed being offered and whether this help and support successfully prevents the repeated removal of children from a mother.

As it currently stands, the local authority in which the mother resides should refer her to independent, local and national support groups and other possible sources of help. If this is not taken up by the parents due to refusal or non-engagement, the social worker must record their efforts to persuade the mother on the case file. At this point, all support plans are directed towards the new adoptive parents and the involved child (Gov.uk, 2013). The birth mother is eligible for support should she engage, but it is not mandatory for any support to be in place for her, just the need to record the social workers efforts.

1.3 Rationale

I have grown up with social care being present in my life, as my mother was a foster carer, for many years throughout my childhood. I then made the decision with my family that we also wanted to support a young child when their life was becoming difficult. We did this for many years looking after babies aged 0-2 as foster carers. We then progressed as a family to adoption, adopting one of our foster babies, and this caused me some anxiety as to how I prevent the cycle of care from repeating with my young person. I began this journey into social work to advocate for at least one more young person.

According to a research study carried out by the European Child and Adolescent Psychiatry, children who are adopted from care are more likely to experience enduring mental health problems (Paine & Fahey, 2020). Early intervention is the key to minimising the risk factors for adoptees who may have experienced many adverse childhood experiences and multiply moves from birth family and foster placement. Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) can chip away at the qualities needed to be a mother such as self-worth and self-trust that foster autonomy.

Through placement it has become prevalent that most, if not all the children that I work with, have parents who have some historic social care involvement. According to the 'Guardian' one in four mothers are caught in the destructive cycle, of having a child removed by the court, with one mother having a total of 16 children removed due to the fact she was not entitled to any support once the child

is removed (Elgot, 2015). This figure can rise to one in three if the mother was a teenager at the time of their baby's birth (Elgot, 2015). The Pause project also highlights that there is a gap in services and support for mothers who have had babies removed, stating there are limitations in present systems of support which allow mothers to fall through the gaps between services. This results in a lack of intervention and any needs the mother may have, not being met (Pause, 2023).

Chapter 2: Methodology

My question 'How are mothers whose babies are removed at birth being supported by social workers?' is focused on mothers whose babies are removed from them and placed in care. I focused on mothers as the primary carers under the definition according to the Oxford English dictionary as a female parent in relation to a child, who she has given birth to. Initially I started my research curious about how social workers can break the cycle of 'being in care', as it appears a large majority of cases I work with have parents who have also had episodes of 'being in care'.

The primary research to explore this topic included focusing my research on care leavers as I hoped that their first-hand experience would allow me to analyse the factors that have the potential to break the cycle. I recognised on reflection that this might re-traumatise or unsettle care leavers and I very much doubted I would receive ethical approval. I also considered that this was a subject many experienced social workers would have an insightful view on. However, I was concerned about unconscious bias and whether I would be able to source experienced social workers with an impartial view, who are not despondent. I then shifted my research approach to explore carrying out literature review. My initial thoughts relating to my research project appeared broad, and I needed to narrow this down considerably. I began this research on October 18th, 2023, using the online London Metropolitan University Library and the search engine Google, researching with titles such as 'breaking the cycle' and 'the emotional cost of children in care'. This did result in articles relating to trauma, such as permanency and well-being outcomes for maltreated infants. I then came across an organisation called 'Pause' and their report "Never More Than Once". This report was a turning point for me, and I began to realise I was trying to research a question which had many rabbit holes I was descending into. On the 28th, October 2023 I discovered I had almost lost sight of my topic and was now searching with key words such as 'trauma'. With the help from my dissertation supervisor, I was able to recognise this, and I took some steps backwards to understand what a 6000-word literature review would allow me to research. According to (Aveyard,2023) there are more than 35 named approaches to a review method. One of them being a systematic review, a systematic review is a concise synopsis of all the relevant evidence available to answer a specific clinical question. The Cochrane Collaboration, established in 1993 are the best known for their method of conducting a systematic review (Aveyard,2023). To conduct a systematic review, I would need a team of researchers and leave no stone unturned in my search for available evidence. Since this is not within my capability being a novice researcher, I decided to apply the principles and guidelines of this approach to construct a literature review that identifies,

critiques, and analyses the literature but is considerably less detailed than a Cochrane style systematic review due to my limited research.

This approach allowed me to narrow down my question, and in my search develop inclusion and exclusion criteria I excluded articles relating to families, fathers, and trauma and most of my previously identified articles. I now searched with a clear inclusion requirement using key terms such as social work, mothers, supported, baby removal (See the below table).

Inclusion	Exclusion
<p>Mothers/ Mums</p> <p>Recurrent /Repeated</p> <p>Baby removal</p> <p>Support</p> <p>Social worker</p> <p>Child protection</p> <p>Pre-birth</p> <p>Vulnerable birth mothers</p>	<p>Dads/ Fathers</p> <p>International</p> <p>Contact</p> <p>Children</p>

Fig 1. Table to should the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this research.

On the 23rd of November 2023 I was fortunate to be introduced to an employee of Pause who kindly sent me 2 articles, which were directly relevant. On the 10th February I revisited the London Met library, using the advanced search, and added ‘social work’ and ‘baby removal’ which gave me 5 articles, 1 of which was relevant. I then added the key term ‘consequences’ which gave me a further 50 articles with only 1 being relevant. This proving to be an extensive area of research, I returned to the original article written by the Pause project and began to review those references to find additional research material and found 1 article of interest. On 10th of February using the search engine Google I searched my question; this gave me my 6th and final article.

When analysing the data in the article, I used the Thematic Analysis approach, as stated in (Braun and Clarke,2022). there are 6 phases to thematic analysis, first being to familiarise myself with the data, generating codes, searching for themes, then reviewing these themes, naming and defining these themes, and finally producing the report. To summarise my use of thematic analysis; I read every article some twice, writing down different initial thoughts. Secondly is generating codes, this for me was an inclusive approach using keywords I had used in my initial search, removals, statistics, support, recurrent and this allowed me to notice immerging patterns in my literature. I became saturated in my literature and was able to recognise core themes. Using colour coding to track them across various pieces of literature. I then grouped my findings into four themes which were pre pregnancy, during pregnancy, post pregnancy and post court.

Chapter 3: Findings & Discussion

3.1 Introduction

In England there is no statutory requirement to support parents once a child is taken into care apart from a small number of cases of adoption' (Pause, 2023, p5). Additionally, there is no methods to track the recurrent cases resulting in a lack of data and analysis regarding repeated removals, which if available could allow for the root cause analysis to improve our understanding of how to tackle this issue. Unfortunately, local authorities are not required to record or collate data relating to and the number of recurrent removals to the government. The Government does not produce any statistics themselves, and finally family courts do not record recurrent cases either (Pause, 2023). This does not reflect the fact that this is a national issue and support for mothers who had babies removed from their care has clearly been identified as a need. I have approached this using the different stages of motherhood to look at what support is currently available within each stage.

3.2 Prenatal

Pause states, that children who have spent time in the care system are at a greater risk of having recurrent care proceedings and multiple children removed as adults (Pause, 2023). If we consider that children who have spent time in care, are likely to have experienced exposure to neglect and abuse, we can understand that this will have an impact on their emotional regulation and relationship with others.

A study completed by Lancaster University has found that mothers who have experienced Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) are predicted to have poor adult outcomes. Furthermore, the study identified 66% of mothers who have had recurrent child removals, experienced high levels of neglect in childhood, with 53% experiencing sexual abuse (Broadhurst et al., 2017). These statistics, along with the advice from the World Health Organisation (WHO), who define sexual health as a state of a person's physical emotional mental and social well-being, it seems likely that many of these mothers do not have adequate sexual health.

Sexual health is possible when a person has a positive and respectful approach to sexual relationships, free from coercion and violence (Gov.uk, 2022). To achieve this children and young people need educating from a young age either through positive role models or personal experience.

Comprehensive sexual education gives age-appropriate information about sexual health and the reproductive system as well as healthy relationships. This education begins at a young age, as children learn to recognise their emotions, while living and experiencing family life and relationships. This would include decision making the principles of consent and what to do if bullying or abuse occur (WHO, 2023).

It is likely that children who have lived in chaotic homes, experienced ACEs and have spent some time in care, have potentially not experienced the positive influences of comprehensive sexual education. Additionally, the report, 'Vulnerable birth mothers and recurrent care proceedings' funded by the Nuffield foundation, suggested that women with persistent difficulties stemming from their early childhood experiences are at risk of having low expectations for themselves and in their relationships leaving them at risk of forming unhealthy intimate relationships. The report findings went further to suggest that the care system did not support this identified group of women to delay or plan wanted pregnancies. It concluded that 'care experienced women' were at a greater risk of having children removed at an early opportunity (Broadhurst, 2017).

3.3 Antenatal

The Waltham Forest pre-birth assessment guidance, states that, 'research and experience indicate that very young babies are extremely vulnerable to abuse and that work carried out in the antenatal period to assess risk and intervention will help to minimise harm' (Waltham Forest). The Children Act 1989 additionally states there are grounds for intervention are, if there is a likelihood of significant harm ensuring the child's needs are paramount.

This assessment will seek to assess the capability of the mother and identify the potential risk to the unborn child. This multi-agency assessment is led by children's social care in collaboration with parents and extended family. However, throughout my research it has been suggested multiple times that care experienced mothers are likely to suffer stress and anxiety (Broadhurst, 2017), due to triggered memories of their own frightening, negative childhood and have potentially delayed telling children's services due to the fear of the consequences. Understanding they are fearful of their own child entering the care system where they have had a negative experience. Furthermore, being known to children's services may evoke fear of preconceptions about their parenting capability.

A smaller number of pregnant women have notified children's services early on in their pregnancies, in the hope of having the largest window of time to prove they have indeed made changes. (Broadhurst,

2017) Whilst local authority guidelines vary regarding the favourable time to conduct a pre-birth assessment, many recommend the child protection conference is held around 18 -20 weeks, gestation, but some are as late as 32 weeks. This gives the parent a short window of time to implement and demonstrate any changes in their behaviour or lifestyle.

Whilst doing this research I found very little information relating to supporting a pregnant mother, other than a service known as 'The Family Nurse Partnership'. Which is a preventative programme, offered to young mothers who are under 19 years of age; Intervention begins early in a mother's pregnancy and remains in place for the babies first year. This high, intensive programme aims to improve a mother's antenatal health, whilst improving the mother's economic self-sufficiency, and break the cycle of disadvantage. Their vision is that every baby, child, and young parent can fulfil their full potential and contribute to society (CWDC).

3.4 Postnatal

When discussing postnatal, I am referring to a mother having carried her unborn baby for the duration of her pregnancy gestation and delivered the baby safely into the world. Throughout my research many if not all the articles refer to the mother post removal of her baby, with one study including quotes from the birth mothers (Broadhurst & Mason, 2020). The quotes shared experiences of suicidal thoughts and feelings of emptiness with no reason to get up in the mornings. Their lives were frequently being characterised by a profound sense of loss and grief. These feelings are then a catalyst for the mothers' lives to become even more chaotic than they previously were, with one mother stating "I was having sex with everyone... I weren't living life... because I felt so alone" and another "So going out, drinking, doing drugs having a laugh makes you forget what you are going through" (Broadhurst & Mason, 2020, p24). Substance misuse to block out feelings as a coping mechanism was a commonality across all the articles.

The Children and Families Act 2014 introduced a 26-week deadline for care proceedings with the hope of shortening this timeframe, and on average repeat proceedings have proven to be 3 weeks shorter than the 26 weeks. This timeframe considers the child's needs, but does not take the mother's needs, who is required to make and prove the identified changes in her lifestyle choices, into consideration (Broadhurst et al., 2017). This is not conducive with research evidence that indicates a longer timeframe is required for any longer-term recovery of substance misuse and serious mental health issues. The lack of attention given to a mother's needs is detrimental to her well-being and recovery (Broadhurst et al., 2017).

Additionally, a common thread across all the articles was the mothers need to fill the void or replace the baby with a subsequent pregnancy within a short window of time. Due to the lack of evidence relating to the effect on a mother who has lost a baby or child to the care system, logical thinkers have likened it to the studies on the impact of perinatal loss and child death (Broadhurst et al., 2015). The logic behind the thinking is that mothers who have been separated from baby or child might be compared to mothers who are bereaved through miscarriage or stillbirth. A key finding in this research is that mothers experiencing grief would often become pregnant with in 12 months of the loss of their child with the report concluding that this subsequent pregnancy lessened the sense of grief (Broadhurst, 2015). Social workers are inherently aware of this connection the term 'replacement baby syndrome' often used to describe mothers whose baby is in care proceedings and rapidly fall pregnant again.

Whilst researching support for mothers at this juncture and considering the full effects having a baby removed, I have also considered the perceptions of the social workers involved in the assessment of the mothers with many reporting the disengagement of mothers; "how do you effect change when they don't talk to you, or hate you" (CWDC ,2013 p.14) and other practitioners and going further to describe parents as being defiant, aggressive whilst lacking insight into why they cannot parent their child and blaming social services for all their problems (CWDC, 2013).

Although support appears to be required it is not mandatory and is often delivered by an outsourced agency rather than the statutory social workers. In New Zealand there is a practice where community-based workers deliver an ecological and relational service (Keddell et al., 2023). This intensive in-home service focuses on reducing stress, drawing on the children being motivation for change. The trusted friend-like relationships are equally respectful and non-judgemental, challenging mothers to be accountable for their personal change goals. (Keddell et al., 2023) The community-based workers additional role is as mediator between statutory child services and the mother, firstly by providing reports, secondly by teaching the mother the 'rules of the game' such as how a mother's actions are perceived by child services. Thirdly making sure the expectations of child services is clear to the mothers. And lastly but no means least, advocating for the mother involved (Keddell et al.,2023).

3.5 Post court proceedings

This consists of the period after a final order has been granted and the baby or child has been placed in alternative permanence away from its biological mother. Often the mother has a feeling of grief compounded by the social stigma of suspicion and speculation from other parents (Broadhurst, 2017).

This loss extends beyond the loss of the child but to the mothers' identity; She is no longer a mother to her child in the remit of the law. This identity loss is frequently paired with fractured extended family relationships due to their loss as a grandparent or aunt, lack of willingness, capacity or approval to care for the child. Research (Broadhurst & Mason, 2020), highlights a further loss financially, as mothers who have had their child removed are no longer entitled to the previously received benefits or housing entitlements. This loss has the potential to negatively impact lifestyle and wellbeing and may put her at risk of loss of income and risk to becoming homeless (Broadhurst, 2017). As noted previously when mothers with evidently increased vulnerability, are under stress they are likely to resort back to previous coping mechanisms such as substance misuse.

At this point in the mother's journey, it is reported that local authorities can signpost mothers to post adoption support, which again is voluntary not mandatory. If the care order is for kinship or connected persons, the referral is not usually offered. The programme I plan to discuss firstly is 'Pause Project', a voluntary organisation where education and support is offered to mothers who are at risk of having their children removed by children's services. Across 151 local authorities, 29 currently have pause projects operating, 45 have a different support service for birth parents and the remaining 77 offer no support (Pause, 2023, p.11) this indicates a postcode lottery of support that mothers can access.

The support Pause offer is expected to run for 18 months with mothers strongly persuaded to take a Long-Acting Reversible Contraceptive (LARC). Although taking LARC is not a condition to receiving the support, many mothers felt they had little autonomy, and it was indeed more persuasive, one might even say coercive. (Gov.uk, 2020) Mothers report unwanted side effects from the LARC but continue with the contraception as the benefits of the help they are receiving outweigh the side effects (Gov.uk, 2020). A further study notes that eligibility for the support is essentially conditional as pregnancy during the supported period can result in the service being withdrawn, increasing the vulnerability of is already vulnerable group of women (Broadhurst et al., 2015). Arguably this raises the ethical question of where the boundary of manipulation and persuasion, lies with the temptation to coerce vulnerable mothers in to terminating pregnancies or delaying future pregnancies. Project Prevention in the US has gone a step further with an initiative to offer a considerable financial reward to substance addicts as an incentive to uptake on sterilisation. Critics of this initiative argue that this does not look at the rehabilitation of the individual but merely exploits their vulnerability by offering short-term gratification and financial gain (Broadhurst et al., 2015).

3.6 Discussion

A reoccurring theme throughout my research has been the prevalence of mothers having had experienced many Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE). According to Manchester University NHS, ACEs are highly stressful traumatic events or situations which can be prolonged threats or single incidents that occur during childhood or adolescence that rupture a young person's trust, security, and safety (Manchester University, NHS). Examples of ACEs are sexual abuse, physical abuse, emotional abuse, living with someone who abuses drugs or alcohol, exposure to domestic violence, living with someone who has a mental illness, and losing a parent through prison divorce or death. Toxic stress from ACEs can impact brain development and affect how the body responds to stress. (Murphy et al., 2017 cited in Broadhurst et al., 2017, p.7) states 'multiple and enduring harms in the context of a child's primary caregiver relationship are firmly established as highly consequential for children's development and subsequent adult functioning'. Furthermore, the exposure to abuse and neglect can impact a person's ability to self-regulate their emotions and build relationships with others. Additional consequences of this negative exposure are the inability to concentrate, think and learn (Broadhurst, 2017).

Whilst considering the previously mentioned effects of ACEs it is important to discuss Erik Erickson's psychosocial theory. Erikson (1902 -1994) was a German American developmental psychologist, known for developing psychosocial theory of the interrelationship between a person's social environment and their psychology, suggesting that the way in which a child is cared for by their caregiver will transfer values and cultural norms (Deacon & Macdonald, 2017).

Erikson emphasised the importance of understanding that the development of personality, continues into adulthood. He continues this thought by outlining that identity develops through stages of 'crisis points' in our lives as we age. According to Erikson 'the actual outcome for any individual would depend on how well that particular 'crisis', or challenge, of that stage was met' (Beckett & Taylor, 2010, p36 cited in Deacon & Macdonald, 2017, p61) This psychosocial theory refers to social expectations and a person's ability at that stage of their development to manage and resolve that crisis.

Erikson believed that there are eight stages of development, and for a person to successfully navigate a crisis a balance must be achieved between two polarities. Although there are eight stages that Erikson identified, the stages relevant to my research are 1- 6 which is up to age 40, as this is when a women's chances of getting pregnant reduces to 5% (Brim, 2024).

The first stage is birth -18 months referred to as 'trust versus mistrust', where babies learn to trust their caregiver and surroundings (Deacon & Macdonald, 2017). The 2nd stage is, 'autonomy versus shame' at approximately 18months – 3years, where a child learns self-control like potty training, it is vital at this point the caregiver offer support and have clear boundaries for a child to develop confidence (Parish, 2014). The next stage is at aged 3-5 and is described as 'initiative versus guilt', harsh criticism and unrealistic expectations at this stage could result in this stage not being met, and the result in the child being unable to self-regulate their emotions (Parish, 2014).The 4th stage Erikson identified, is 'industry versus inferiority', between the ages of 5 and 12. At this stage children begin to see their function in the world and if reactions surrounding them are inconsistent or negative the child will likely to grow up feeling incompetent with lifelong feelings of inadequacy (Deacon & Macdonald, 2017). The next stage at approximately 12-20 is known as 'identity versus role confusion', during this stage teenagers will affiliate themselves with certain groups to express themselves. This experimental stage needs supporting for the young person to see their importance and to be able to contribute to society (Parish, 2017). The final stage relevant to this research, is 'intimacy versus isolation', Erikson believed this stage spanned the ages of 20-40 years. If a young person has unsuccessfully navigated the previous stages, it is likely they will be insecure in their own identity and take risks relating to social interactions and intimacy.

With Erikson in mind, the consequences of these stages not being met, may explain some of the behaviours I have previously mentioned in the findings, such as the mother having little trust in those around her who are trying to support her, having unregulated emotions, poor coping mechanisms, substance misuse and immaturity. The key elements of the lifespan perspective shed further light on this. Firstly, that all individuals have plasticity at all ages and have the capacity for change responding to environmental demands. Secondly, that research from interdisciplinary perspectives is needed to fully understand an individual's lifespan development. And lastly, that an individual's development happens within interrelated contexts such as family, culture and nature (Boyd & Bee,2019). With this thought in mind, the issue of repeat removals cannot be addressed in isolation, more support is needed to address the traumas that have happened across an individual's lifespan and support should be being offered on a mandatory basis. Affording mothers the opportunity to process any unresolved stages of development, and past trauma could in turn promote their agency and increase the likelihood of a mother making the necessary changes to keep their babies.

At present the support being offered is a postcode lottery, with many local authorities not having any supportive scheme in place and what is available comes with potentially unethical conditions. As

previously mentioned, Pause has been described as almost coercive in its insistence for a mother to take the LARC (Gov.uk, 2020). This type of condition such as taking a LARC along with the withdrawal of support should the mother get pregnant, and the postcode lottery appears to go against British Association of Social Workers (BASW) code of ethics, requires that social workers act ethically, respect human rights and promote social justice. In the Human rights act (1989) Article 2 protects a person's right to life and Article 8 protects a person's right to their private life and family life (Equality and Human rights commission, 2018). In practice, social workers following the BASW code of ethics, aim to address inequalities and injustices that exist in society, it is imperative that social worker involvement includes social pedagogical work and therapeutic work with these mothers (BASW, 2021). It is our duty to promote and support a mother's dignity and rights to make a decision and make their own choices, whilst challenging oppression.

An additional thought is to address is the issue of young care leavers, getting pregnant or preventing them from repeating the cycle. A possible solution is for foster carers to engage in regular training on promoting sexual health, but at present it would depend on the foster carer building a relationship with the young person and being prepared to have open discussions. A factor that could hinder the relationship between foster carer and young person is the placement stability. The national Institute for Health and Care Excellence report addressing placement stability, quote that 29% of looked after children and young people were in long-term placement in March 2018, and 50% of long-term placements for teenagers had broken down. This placement breakdown could be prevented if more local authorities delivered the Mockingbird programme. The Mockingbird programme aims to build a constellation community where relationships are nurtured between children, young people and foster families supporting them to build resilient and caring, communities of six to ten foster families (The Fostering Network, 2022). This vital peer support empowers families, to overcome issues before they escalate and supports a diversity of placements.

Additionally, if the young person is in foster care, and is unable to discuss these matters with their foster carers there should be a meaningful relationship built between the young person and their social worker. This also has its barriers, according to children's social care workforce (2022), there is an increase in the turnover rate of full time employed social workers with many leaving local authorities after 5 years. Of the 3,630 social workers who left local authority in 2021, 23% moved to agency roles. Working for an agency gives the social worker more flexibility to move around causing instability to the relationship and children and families have highlighted that this frequent change of social worker

caused delays and felt a lack of support, with the children quoting they do not get enough time to know you (Kulakiewicz et al., 2022).

This research also suggested a further issue, that the use of agency social workers may be the cause of over a £100 million loss per year to local authorities that could be better spent on front-line activity such as preventative measures (Kulakiewicz et al., 2022). This overspending is highlighted in the National Children's Bureau, stating that local authorities across England had increased their spending on children's services by £800 million in the years 2021/22 that is an increase of 8% on the previous year (National Children's Bureau, 2023). Analysis of data identified that despite the increased spending, £4 of every £5 spent went on late intervention, with major children's charities witnessing a startling decline in early intervention services of over 46% from the previous 12 years. Early interventions such as Pause, use an evidently more cost-effective way to implement preventative measures to protect the repeated removals of babies. The Department for Education (DfE) evaluation of Pause has identified that the cost of implementing Pause saves double the cost of child proceedings, which were estimated as in 2020 £39,141. This evaluation additionally established that for every £1 Pause spent, £4.50 was saved in child protection (DfE, 2020). When you consider this saving against the 107,317 children in social care across the UK in March 2023, it seems pertinent to already question why this service is not statutory.

This lack of investment in our children and families' service is a prime example of social harm through the zemiological lens, as the government must ask parliament for money it wants to spend that year, the government then divides this money up between local authorities, and local authorities then decide how they spend the money (UK Parliament, 2024). These decisions on spending have a significant impact on the mothers and their babies with all requests for support for the mothers needing to be presented by a qualified social worker at a funding panel. These much-criticised panels have questionable legality while making impactful decisions regarding eligibility and care planning with little understanding of the full consequences of funding being declined (Clements, 2024).

Chapter 4: Conclusion

Through this research I have found there is little support available from statutory social workers, for young women pre-pregnancy, during pregnancy, and post child removal. I have discovered that the support available is usually delivered by an outsourced agency and not delivered as mandatory by statutory social workers. Limited support is available pre-pregnancy from the leaving care team, in the form of education relating to positive relationships. Additionally, there was a clear understanding of the consequential effects to mothers who have experienced past traumas, with few suggestions of supporting mothers to address those traumas. What is available comes with unethical conditions (Broadhurst, 2015). It is not consistently available to all women, as it will depend on whether your local authority has a practice operating within its borough.

As suggested in the Guardian (2012), if mothers had their own social worker who could make representation and advocate for them, while the baby or child had a separate social worker this would mean the child's social worker is able to keep the needs of the child paramount whilst the mother is also receiving support. The Guardian went further to state that Professor Eileen Munro agreed to the benefits of separate social workers within the same family, but the financial implications of the resources required to implement such a policy clearly outweighed the benefits. Social workers should lean towards asking 'What has happened to you?' not 'What is wrong with you?' (Boyd, 2022)

Consequently a 'Trauma informed approach' that prioritises the mother's physical and emotional safety is paramount, as is building trust, being honest and reliable, setting clear boundaries ensuring the mother feels valued and empowered (MacFarlane, 2023). This knowledge should be a mandatory module of all social work degrees if we are to have any success in breaking the cycle of multiple baby removals from mothers.

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